

Fuel consumption reduction in marine power systems through thermoelectric energy recovery

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Abstract

Similar to aircraft applications, the reduction of fuel consumption in marine power systems is of great importance, because it leads to reduction in CO₂ emissions, in travel costs and so to optimal use of fossil fuels. Moreover, the ship autonomy becomes higher. In the ECOMARINE project, in order to maximize electricity production by waste heat recovery and to simultaneously improve electric power quality, the introduction of a supplementary thermoelectric energy recovery unit is being implemented. The heat of the produced gases from a diesel generator is directly converted to electrical energy with the use of a thermoelectric generator. The typical temperature of the exhaust gases is over 300°C, thus their temperature difference from the ambient temperature corresponds to a typical thermoelectric module's operating temperature difference. The generated voltage of the module drops with the increase of its current; hence an MPPT is required in order to achieve the maximum power output. Although ZT~ 1 materials do not provide in general the thermal efficiency and system costs to be the long term solution to industrial scale waste heat recovery, in the particular case of marine energy production, where special conditions apply, they could serve as sustainable prototype energy system components. Advanced TE materials having ZT~ 2 properties that have recently been developed and characterized and new advanced TE materials with ZT~ 4 envisioned in the long-term future will strongly enhance TEG commercialization.

Introduction

Even when accounting for all environmental impacts, ships are still the most efficient mode of transport. More than 80% of all goods shipped in the world are transported on ships. Ship transport generates a large amount of waste heat, which is today to some extent utilized as thermal and rarely as electrical energy. Ships normally have waste heat of a quantity and quality to cover all demands for thermal energy on-board. This makes electrical power generation from waste heat interesting. Turbine-based systems exist, but these need large engines to be attractive. However for smaller engines and other waste heat sources, thermoelectric generators (TEGs) represent a promising solution. Clearly important factors for success in applying TEGs are commercialization of results from materials research and reduced price/Watt power output of the TEGs.

Various technologies, including thermoelectric technologies, are being considered to recover and convert the industrial process waste energy to useful electrical energy. Thermoelectric (TE) materials, discovered in 1821, are semiconductor solids that produce an electric current when joined together and subjected to a temperature difference across the junction. This property makes it possible to produce direct current electricity by applying waste heat on one side of a TE material, while exposing the other side to lower or ambient temperature surroundings. TE materials available prior to about 1995 produced thermal-to-electric

conversion efficiencies in the 2% to 5% range and were only used in small niche applications. However, recent significant advances in the scientific understanding of quantum well and nanostructure effects on TE properties and modern thin layer and nano-scale manufacturing technologies have combined to create the opportunity of advanced TE materials with potential conversion efficiencies of over 15%. The advent of these advanced TE materials offers new opportunities to recover waste heat more efficiently and economically with highly reliable and relatively passive systems that produce no noise and vibration, as TE generators (TEG) contain no moving parts, a fact which makes them extremely reliable and scalable. The technology has therefore aroused worldwide interest in many fields, including waste heat recovery and solar heat utilization (power generation mode), and temperature-controlled seats, portable picnic coolers and thermal management in microprocessors (active refrigeration mode) [1].

The efficiency of TE devices is strongly associated with the dimensionless figure of merit (ZT) of TE materials, defined as $ZT = (\alpha^2 \sigma / K) T$, where $\alpha = \Delta V / \Delta T$ and σ , K and T are the electrical resistivity, thermal conductivity and absolute temperature respectively. High electrical conductivity (corresponding to low Joule heating), a large Seebeck coefficient (corresponding to large potential difference) and low thermal conductivity (corresponding to a large temperature difference) are therefore necessary in order to realize high-performance TE materials (Figure 2). The ZT figure is also a very convenient indicator for evaluating the potential efficiency of TE devices. In general, good TE materials have a ZT value of close to unity. However, ZT values of up to three are considered to be essential for TE energy converters that can compete on efficiency with mechanical power generation and active refrigeration. High-performance TE materials have been pursued since Bi_2Te_3 -based alloys were discovered in the 1960s. Until the end of last century, moderate progress had been made in the development of TE materials.

Figure 1: Crystal structure of Sb_2Te_3 [7]

The benchmark of $ZT \approx 1$ was broken in the mid-1990s by two different research approaches: one by exploring new materials with complex crystalline structures, and the other by reducing the dimensions of the materials. The search for new materials, such as skutterudites and clathrates, is mainly motivated by the suggestion of Slack [3]. In those compounds, the 'rattling' motion of loosely bonded atoms within a large cage generates strong scattering against lattice phonon propagation, but has less of an impact on the transport of electrons. As a consequence, the thermal conductivity of

skutterudites and clathrates can be reduced greatly while maintaining the electrical conductivity at a high level. Zintl compounds with a large unit cell, including $\text{Yb}_{14}\text{MnSb}_{11}$, $\text{Yb}_{11}\text{GaSb}_9$, $\text{Ca}_{11}\text{GaSb}_9$ and SrZnSb_2 have also been revealed to possess an intrinsically low lattice thermal conductivity due to the high fraction of low-velocity optical phonon modes [4].

Figure 2: Recent developments in ZT improvement [2]

Figure 3: Typical skutterudite structure [10]

In research on low-dimensional material systems, Dresselhaus et al. [5] suggested that the power factor ($\alpha^2\sigma$) can be enhanced through the use of quantum-confinement effects. As the system size decreases and approaches a nanometer length scale, the density of electronic states (DOS) can split and become narrow. Dresselhaus's pioneering work has shed light on various low-dimensional systems, including superlattices, nanowires and quantum dots. Venkatasubramanian et al. [6] reported Bi_2Te_3/Sb_2Te_3 superlattices with a high-ZT value of up to 2.4. Subsequently, Harman et al. [7] reported $PbTe/PbTeSe$ quantum dot superlattices with a ZT value of greater than 3.0 at 600 K. However, for general applications, it is highly desired to develop high-performance bulk TE materials. The latest advancements in TE technology focuses on nanostructural approaches, highlighting the potential routes for improvement in the major TE material systems, including Bi-Te alloys, skutterudites, Ag-Pb-Sb-Te or 'LAST', half-Heusler alloys and some high-ZT oxides. Along these lines, p-type half-Heusler alloys were mostly based on the formula $MCoSb$, where M is Ti, Zr, or Hf. The high substitutability of the three lattice sites (M, Co, and Sb) provides many opportunities for tuning the electronic and lattice properties of the half-Heuslers. Through partial elemental substitution, the large lattice thermal conductivity of half-Heusler compounds is expected to be greatly reduced due to mass fluctuation and strain field effects. However, the thermal conductivity of p-type half-Heusler alloys reported so far still remains very high (higher than $4Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$), which prevents ZT from reaching a meaningful value. The highest ZT of about 0.5 in p-type $Zr_{0.5}Hf_{0.5}CoSb_{0.8}Sn_{0.2}$ was achieved at 1000 K with a thermal conductivity of $4.1Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$ at 300 K and $3.6Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$ at 1000 K. Such a thermal conductivity is still very high due to mainly the contribution of lattice thermal conductivity [8].

TEG in aerospace applications

In the last years, helicopters have grown to become very popular, not only for special missions, such as medical emergencies, law enforcement and civil protection, but also for general transportation use. Under this context, the improvement of their efficiency as well as the idea of a "more electric aircraft" (MEA) have been promoted. The use of higher voltages in helicopters has facilitated the concept of the MEA, because the electrical grid of the helicopter has to support the growing load demands introduced by the conversion of instruments, which were previously powered mechanically or hydraulically. Furthermore the electrical power generation efficiency now plays a significant role to the whole helicopter efficiency, fuel usage and carbon impact. In current helicopters, for reliability reasons, at least two electrical generators operating at half their nominal power are used to supply the

necessary power to the grid. These machines are connected to the main gear box, which has a direct cost in fuel burning. As a result new and more efficient power supply methods are needed. Waste heat energy recovery systems, which take advantage of the main engine exhaust gases, have already been applied in ground vehicles. However they have never been used before in aircrafts, where the requirements are very strict. Our research team has introduced an innovative method of energy recovery based on TE technology in the context of Clean Sky “RENERGISE” project. The exhaust gases contain a great amount of energy in the form of heat, as their temperature is around 570°C under normal operation. A fraction of this energy remains can be exploited with the use of thermoelectric generators. The energy is then injected to the DC bus through a power electronics converter. What is more, the highly energetic, high temperature gases can be used to rotate an electrical generator thanks to a turbine using steam generated by a boiler placed at the engine nozzle [7]. Furthermore, in the context of Clean Sky ‘THERMICOOL’ we are aiming to develop an innovative TE cooler for avionic application with maturity level TRL5, low power consumption and high efficiency and a combination of thermoelectric materials and energy harvesting techniques. The work will investigate advanced TE materials with $ZT \gg 1$, in multistage module configurations to cope with the harsh avionic environment and novel active control schemes to achieve high COP values.

TEG in marine applications

Similar to aircraft applications, the reduction of fuel consumption in marine power systems is of great importance, because it leads to reduction in CO₂ emissions, in travel costs and so to optimal use of fossil fuels. Moreover, the ship autonomy becomes higher. Today, the most common energy saving solutions that have been applied in marine power systems are based on the cogeneration of heat and power (CHP) scheme, i.e. the wasted heat during the operation of diesel generators is used for the ship’s thermal and/or cooling needs. Additionally, a recent energy saving concept for marine power systems is based on the introduction of an exhaust gas boiler that supplies steam to a steam turbine, increasing so electrical energy production about 10%.

In thermoelectric generation applications, the two indispensable conditions are the hot source and the cold source to provide the temperature difference for the generator. In other words, the larger the temperature difference between the hot and the cold, the better power performance of the TEG. In this sense, the waste heat recovery from various high temperature gas or steam turbines on ships by TEG is very promising because the ocean naturally plays a role as an infinitely large and almost zero cost cold source. In these marine power plants, in principle it is easier to build and keep the needed temperature difference for TEG. Additionally the isolation from the commercial electric grid during the cruising potentially makes a greater demand for TEG as a complementary DC power supply on ships

In the ECOMARINE project, in order to maximize electricity production by waste heat recovery and to simultaneously improve electric power quality, the introduction of a supplementary thermoelectric energy recovery unit is being implemented. The heat of the produced gases from a diesel generator is directly converted to electrical energy with the use of a thermoelectric generator. The typical temperature of the exhaust gases is over 300°C, thus their temperature difference from the ambient temperature corresponds to a typical thermoelectric module’s operating temperature difference. The generated voltage of the module drops with the increase of its current; hence an MPPT is required in order to achieve the maximum power output. Consequently, with the use of the above energy recovery system, fuel consumption as well as carbon emissions are decreased, improving so the efficiency of the marine power system.

Figure 4: ECOMARINE Project Overview [11]

The experimental TEG setup is based on 750 units of the GM250-127-28-10 TEG with the following operational parameters ($\Delta T=220^{\circ}\text{C}$)

- Matched Load Output Power 28.3W
- Matched Load Resistance $0.42\Omega \pm 15\%$
- Open Circuit Voltage 6.9V
- Matched Load Output Current 8.2A
- Matched Load Output Voltage 3.45V
- Heat Flow Through Module $\sim 566\text{W}$

The heat exchanger constructed is a tubular jacket $\text{Ø}500$ with a glycol-based primary cooling medium, whereas the secondary cooling medium is sea-water. However, waste flue gas streams are typically near atmospheric pressure and in large cross-section flues ($\text{Ø}500$ in our case). These conditions do not provide the fluid dynamics required to generate high heat flux transfer. In general, efficient heat transfer technologies and techniques are needed to enable high heat transfer with low temperature differentials between the exhaust gas streams and the TE device hot side. This will allow the TE device hot side to match the temperature of the exhaust gas stream more closely, thereby increasing the system performance (i.e., efficiency and power output). It is anticipated that hot-side pumping power will be required to achieve the necessary flow and heat transfer rates. At this stage our initial calculations indicate a conversion efficiency of 6.4%. Consequently during phase I of the ECOMARINE experimental measurements we expect a waste heat recovery of 1.2%. This results to a generated (recovered) electrical energy of 20.3 KW (for a 1.7 MW diesel G/E).

Figure 5: ECOMARINE calculated performance for experimental setup [11]

Nevertheless, at the end of the project phase II, we expect conversion efficiency ~10%, which will result, depending on the ship type to energy savings from 10% to 50%. This renders the ECOMARINE proposal a worthwhile capital investment with a ROI period of just under 2 years and a useful operational life of approximately 15 years.

Source: American Association of Port Authorities						Availability in 2015							
SHIP TYPE	Average power demand (kW)	Maximum power demand (kW)	Maximum power demand, 95% of ships (kW)	Minimum Effective TEG (kW)	Optimum TEG Generator (kW)	TEG Product Classification (3 Commercial Classes)	Cost in kUSD (best case)	Cost in kUSD (worst case)	Fuel Savings (annual/LSGO Scenario) kUSD	Savings from Maintenance Costs (Annual, kUSD)	Total Savings (Annual, kUSD)	SEEMP Applicability / CO2 reduction	
Containerships (<140m)	170	1000	800	16	80	50	100	150	88,5	0,15	88,6	YES	
Containerships (>140m)	1200	8000	5000	100	500	200	400	600	353,9	0,6	354,5	YES	
Containerships (Total)	800	8000	4000	80	400	200	400	600	353,9	0,6	354,5	YES	
RO---RO ships	1500	2000	1800	36	180	100	200	300	177,0	0,3	177,3	YES	
Tankers	1400	2700	2500	50	250	100	200	300	177,0	0,3	177,3	YES	
Cruise ships (<200m)	4100	7300	6700	134	670	200	400	600	353,9	0,6	354,5	YES	
Cruise ships (>200m)	7500	11000	9500	190	950	200	400	600	353,9	0,6	354,5	YES	
Bulk Carriers	300	1000	850	17	85	50	100	150	88,5	0,15	88,6	YES	
Reefers	600	2000	1700	34	170	100	200	300	177,0	0,3	177,3	YES	
				~10% Energy Savings	~50% Energy Savings				LSGO	1010 USD/t			
									Diesel Generator M&O Annual Costs	3 USD/kW			
									TEG+Converter+Control Costs	3000 USD/kW			
									Fuel Consumption	0,2 kg/kWh			
									Hours per year	8760			
									Cost per KWh	0,202			
									Cost per Year per KWh (USD)	1769,52			

Figure 6: ECOMARINE system financial prospects [11]

Conclusions

In thermoelectric generation applications, the two indispensable conditions are the hot source and the cold source to provide the temperature difference for the generator. In other words, the larger the temperature difference between the hot and the cold, the better power performance of the TEG. In this sense, the waste heat recovery from various high temperature gas or steam turbines on ships by TEG is very promising because the ocean naturally plays a role as an infinitely large and almost zero cost cold source. In these marine power plants, in principle it is easier to build and keep the precious temperature difference for TEG. Additionally the isolation from the commercial electric grid during the cruising potentially makes a greater demand for TEG as a complementary DC power supply on ships.

Although $ZT \sim 1$ materials do not provide in general the thermal efficiency and system costs to be the long term solution to industrial scale waste heat recovery, in the particular case of marine energy production, where the above special conditions apply, they could serve as sustainable prototype energy system components. Advanced TE materials having $ZT \sim 2$ properties that have recently been developed and characterized and new advanced TE materials with $ZT \sim 4$ envisioned in the long-term future will strongly enhance TEG commercialization by providing the thermal conversion efficiencies needed to make TEG economically attractive. Enhanced TEG performance ($ZT \sim 2$ and $>15\%$ thermal efficiency) will provide for a more attractive business case, both for the TEG developer and the marine users.

References

- [1] HoSung Lee, *Thermal Design: Heat Sinks, Thermoelectrics, Heat Pipes, Compact Heat Exchangers, and Solar Cells*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2011
- [2] Jing-Feng Li, Wei-Shu Liu, Li-Dong Zhao and Min Zhou, High-performance nanostructured thermoelectric materials, *NPG Asia Mater.* 2(4) 152–158 (2010), [dx.doi.org/10.1038/asiamat.2010.138](https://doi.org/10.1038/asiamat.2010.138)
- [3] G. A. Slack, in *CRC Handbook of Thermoelectrics*, D. M. Rowe ed. (CRC Press, USA, 1995).
- [4] E. S. Toberer, A. F. May, G. J. Snyder, *Chem. Mater.* 22, 624 (2010).
- [5] L. D. Hicks, M. S. Dresselhaus, *Phys. Rev. B* 47, 12727 (1993).
- [6] R. Venkatasubramanian, E. Siivola, T. Colpitts, B. O'Quinn, *Nature* 413, 597 (2001).
- [7] T. C. Harman, P. J. Taylor, M. P. Walsh, B. E. LaForge, *Science* 297, 2229 (2002).
- [8] Xiao Yan, Giri Joshi, Weishu Liu, Yucheng Lan, Hui Wang, Sangyeop Lee, J. W. Simonson, S. J. Poon, T. M. Tritt, Gang Chen, and Z. F. Ren, Enhanced Thermoelectric Figure of Merit of p-Type Half-Heuslers, *Nano Lett.* 2011, 11, 556–560, [dx.doi.org/10.1021/nl104138t](https://doi.org/10.1021/nl104138t).
- [9] Georgios C. Christidis, Ioannis Ch. Karatzaferis, Ioannis I. Perpinias, Matthieu Sautreuil, Nikolaos P. Papanikolaou, Michael Loupis, Ioannis Spanoudakis and Emmanuel C. Tatakis, Innovative Waste Heat Recovery Systems in Rotorcrafts, International Conference on Electrical Systems for Aircraft, Railway and Ship Propulsion - ESARS 2012 (IEEE), Bologna, 16-18 October 2012, DOI: 10.1109/ESARS.2012.6387452
- [10] Jin-Cheng Zheng, Recent advances on thermoelectric materials, *Front. Phys. China*, 2008, 3(3): 269-279
- [11] ECOMARINE project communications, 2013